

Construction of a medium-deep geothermal storage system: Case study of the SKEWS MD-BTES demosite

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Drilling techniques
Hydraulic hammer
Borehole path deviation
Borehole heat exchanger
Heat storage
Seasonal heat storage
Borehole thermal energy storage
MD-BTES
SKEWS
PUSH-IT

ABSTRACT

The global energy transition toward renewable resources poses particular challenges in the heating sector, where a seasonal mismatch between heat demand and supply remains a critical obstacle. Medium-deep borehole thermal energy storage systems (MD-BTES), installed at depths of 400–1000 m, offer large subsurface storage capacities while avoiding the high costs associated with deep geothermal drilling. To date, the benefits of MD-BTES have been demonstrated primarily through modelling studies, with limited empirical validation. Here, we report the construction and commissioning of the first MD-BTES demonstration site at the Lichtwiese Campus in Darmstadt, Germany. In 2022–2023, three 750 m deep borehole heat exchangers (BHE) were installed in a triangular layout with 8.6 m spacing. When expanded to 37 BHE, with inlet temperatures of 90 °C (summer) and 30 °C (winter), output up to 15 GWh·a⁻¹ and 3.5 MW is achievable with a recovery efficiency up to 75 % after 5 years of operation. During drilling, unforeseen (hydro-)geological conditions, including fault zones and extensively altered crystalline rocks, required a transition from pneumatic and hydraulic down-the-hole hammer drilling to rotary drilling with clay-polymer fluids. Comparative analysis showed that the pneumatic and hydraulic hammer techniques achieved 2 to 5 times higher rates of penetration relative to rotary drilling. Continuous groundwater monitoring revealed a temporary ecological impact from drilling fluids and intermediate cementations, which dissipated after completion. The drilling operations consumed ~90,950 L of diesel fuel, corresponding to ~244 t CO₂ emissions.

These results provide, for the first time, a comprehensive empirical assessment of MD-BTES construction under practical field conditions, enable extended test operations on storage efficiency, and highlighting the need for economically viable vertical and fast drilling technologies for large-scale MD-BTES development.

1. Introduction

As global energy demand continues to rise, coupled with the compelling challenge to mitigate climate change impacts, the transition towards sustainable and renewable energy systems has become a central focus in energy research and policy development (IEA, 2024), (REN, 2025). One of the key challenges in the widespread implementation of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, is their intermittent characteristic, creating discrepancies between energy availability and demand (Denholm et al., 2015). To effectively bridge these gaps, innovative solutions in energy storage are required, enabling a stable and reliable energy supply throughout seasonal fluctuations (Ziegler et al., 2019).

Geothermal energy storage systems arranged in a compact array,

particularly Medium-Deep Borehole Thermal Energy Storage (MD-BTES), represent a promising technology due to their capability of storing and extracting large quantities of thermal energy over seasonal periods (Homuth et al., 2013), (Bär et al., 2015), (Welsch et al., 2015). Seasonal charging and discharging are achieved by conductive heat transfer within a closed-loop fluid circuit that circulates through borehole heat exchangers (BHEs). By reaching moderate depths, typically between 400–1000 m below the surface, MD-BTES balance the cost and complexity associated with deeper geothermal projects with the limited storage capacity of shallow systems (Welsch, 2019). In addition, compared to shallow systems, higher subsurface temperatures are encountered and fewer boreholes are required for the same performance, allowing for urban deployment with a low footprint (Welsch et al., 2016). By insulating the upper pipe section with low thermal

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geothermics.2025.103579>

Received 14 October 2025; Received in revised form 12 December 2025; Accepted 14 December 2025

Available online 18 December 2025

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conductivity cement, the upper aquifer can also be protected against negative thermal influences and efficiency can be increased by minimising thermal losses at high groundwater flow rates (Schulte et al., 2016), (Nguyen et al., 2017). The strategic placement, preferably in crystalline basement, due to high thermal and low hydraulic conductivity, as well as the design of these systems is crucial for their efficiency and overall performance (Schulte et al., 2016). Recent studies have extensively investigated MD-BTES systems, primarily utilizing analytical approaches, numerical modeling, and co-simulation techniques (Schulte et al., 2015), (Schulte et al., 2016), (Nguyen et al., 2017), (Kolo et al., 2024), (Formhals et al., 2022), (Ma et al., 2024). These investigations have targeted the detailed understanding of heat transfer mechanisms within borehole arrays, including conductive and convective processes, thermal dispersion, and the resultant heat propagation through subsurface geological formations. Specific attention was paid to evaluating how geological and hydrogeological parameters, such as thermal conductivity, groundwater flow velocity, and subsurface stratigraphic variability, influence the efficiency, thermal performance, and long-term operational stability of MD-BTES systems.

Further theoretical research has concentrated on optimizing borehole configurations to minimize thermal interference between individual boreholes, thereby improving overall storage capacity and seasonal efficiency (Boockmeyer and Bauer, 2016), (Woloszyn, 2018). Studies by Welsch et al. (2016) highlighted the critical importance of careful design parameters, such as borehole spacing, depth, and arrangement patterns, to achieve sustainability and maximum thermal efficiency of up to 80 %.

Moreover, significant attention has been directed toward the integration of MD-BTES systems into larger-scale energy infrastructures and district heating networks. Formhals et al. (2021) investigated heat transition strategies for a real university campus, showing that the integration of solar thermal generation with a MD-BTES can substantially reduce fossil fuel dependency, enhance the long-term sustainability of district heating systems and reduce the levelized cost of heat from 7.6 ct-kWh⁻¹ to 6.3 ct-kWh⁻¹. In a subsequent study (Formhals et al., 2022), a co-simulation framework coupling district heating models with

detailed 3D subsurface finite element models was developed, demonstrating that accurate modeling of borehole-network interactions is crucial for assessing system flexibility, operational strategies, and long-term performance. Findings from Welsch et al. (2018) indicate that although initial investment costs remain relatively high, long-term operational savings and reduced global warming impact by 54 % significantly enhance the economic and environmental attractiveness of MD-BTES systems compared to traditional heating solutions.

Despite substantial theoretical advances and robust modelling-based findings, empirical validation of MD-BTES technologies through practical implementations remains limited. Consequently, uncertainties persist regarding their technical feasibility and operational behavior under realistic field conditions. To address these uncertainties and experimentally verify theoretical predictions, a research MD-BTES was built at the TU Darmstadt (Campus Lichtwiese), which was funded by the SKEWS project (Seasonal crystalline borehole thermal energy storage, No. 03EE4030A). The planned MD-BTES comprised four BHEs, each with a depth of 750 m, arranged in a triangular layout with a spacing of 5 m (Fig. 1). Due to deviating geological and hydrogeological conditions from the prognosis in the planning phase, costs increased, resulting in only the three BHE 2-4 up to 750 m depth being constructed (Landau et al., 2023). The borehole geometry was derived from an optimization study conducted by Welsch et al. (2016). Additionally, three groundwater monitoring wells (GMW 1–3) were designed to be installed in a triangular configuration surrounding the storage system to monitor chemical and thermal parameters within the groundwater.

A comprehensive scientific investigation program was established, including preliminary geophysical surveys, thin section analyses of cuttings, recording of drilling parameters, borehole geophysical logging, a distributed geothermal response test (dGRT), and a one-year operational testing period consisting of five charging and discharging cycles (Landau et al., 2023), (Seib et al., 2024), (Seib et al., 2025), (Krusemark et al., 2025).

The empirical data obtained from these investigations are used for calibration and validation of structural-geological and numerical

Fig. 1. Location of the SKEWS drilling site at the Campus Lichtwiese at TU Darmstadt. BHE 2–4 have a depth of 750 m and BHE 1 was stopped in 40 m (modified after Krusemark et al. (2025)).

models. Using these validated models, further scaling simulations will be performed to predict the thermal efficiency, economic feasibility, and environmental impact of larger storage configurations. Furthermore, co-simulations with the existing district heating network at Campus Lichtwiese, performed in the follow-up project Push-IT (Piloting Underground Storage of Heat In geoThermal reservoirs, No 101096566), utilize real-time measurement data to investigate optimal integration strategies under varying operational conditions.

The resulting research findings serve as the basis for evaluating the potential expansion of the MD-BTES to 19 BHE or 37 BHE for complete commercial integration into the campus district heating network. Preliminary simulations for a semiannual operating scenario with inlet temperatures of 90 °C in summer and 30 °C in winter indicate that, at these expansion stages, recovery efficiencies of up to 75 % after 5 years are achievable, with a energy output of up to 13-15 GWh·a⁻¹ and a thermal power of 3-3.5 MW (Krusemark et al., 2025).

This paper presents a detailed case study focusing on the construction of the first SKEWS MD-BTES system, which enables large amounts of energy at high medium temperatures. It provides a detailed overview of the key planning phases, permitting processes, measurement programs, the relevant (hydro-)geological site conditions, and a comprehensive analysis of drilling operations, including the potential environmental impacts. The results and experiences documented in this study offer a solid foundation and practical reference for future MD-BTES projects. Finally, insights derived from the SKEWS demonstration project aim to contribute significantly towards a sustainable energy sector by enabling wider acceptance and improved efficiency of MD-BTES technology.

2. Methodology

2.1. Planning and project phases

For the design and implementation of the MD-BTES system in Darmstadt, a structured process consisting of six phases was followed, in alignment with established industry standards (AHO-Arbeitskreis Tiefe Geothermie, 2014) (Fig. 2). Phase 1 with the literature research and the analysis of potential locations began around 2013 and proceeded

continuously into phase 2, during which further geological datasets were analysed, geological analogue studies were carried out, the geothermal potential was determined, and initial preliminary planning with cost analyses was carried out. The final decision for the location in the southeastern part of the Lichtwiese Campus was made in consideration of these results and the spatial conditions. The preliminary exploration and feasibility study of phase 3 began with the geophysical survey of the anticipated site in 2021 to 2022, which included geoelectrical methods, gravimetry, and reflection seismic methods (Seib et al., 2024). In parallel, numerical modelling and parameter sensitivity analyses were performed to optimize the MD-BTES system design specifically for the selected location (Welsch et al., 2016). These findings contributed directly to the formulation of the SKEWS project proposal and the required main operating plan for the mining authority.

Additionally, regulatory permits were obtained, including a water permit from the local water authority, comprehensive environmental and species protection reports, and formal confirmation that the site is excluded as a potential nuclear waste repository. The SKEWS proposal was developed collaboratively with drilling companies, the Leibnitz Institute for Applied Geophysics (LIAG), and the Hessian Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology (HLNUG), significantly improving the technical feasibility, timeline management, and regulatory approval process through direct stakeholder involvement.

The construction of the three groundwater monitoring wells (GMW 1-3), reaching depths of 30 m to 40 m, also served as a smaller test drilling in advance to reach the bedrock horizon. Phase 4, involving the main geothermal drilling operations, is discussed comprehensively in the following chapters (Landau et al., 2023). Some outcomes from phases 5 and 6 have already been published (Seib et al., 2025), (Krusemark et al., 2025), (Krusemark et al., 2025), and further results will be presented in upcoming publications.

2.2. Geology

The site is located on the northern edge of the crystalline Odenwald in the Frankenstein complex of the Bergsträsser Odenwald (Fig. 3) (Stein, 2001). To characterize the reservoir properties, literature data were evaluated and geological outcrop studies and preliminary seismic

Fig. 2. Planning and project phases for the construction of the MD-BTES in Darmstadt after (AHO-Arbeitskreis Tiefe Geothermie 2014).

Fig. 3. Regional (a) and local (b) geological setting of the study area (modified after Seib et al. (2024)).

investigations were conducted at the SKEWS site (Bär et al., 2015), (Fahlbusch, 1980), (Kempe et al., 2001). According to geological maps, the region predominantly comprises granodiorites and granites, with amphibolites and metapelites from the Variscan orogeny expected further to the south (Altherr et al., 1999). These crystalline rocks form the basement of the Sprendlinger Horst located northeast of the study area, an intramontane sedimentary basin composed of post-Variscan Permian basalts and sediments (Bodenforschung, 1989), (Kowalczyk, 2001). The thickness is up to 250 m in the north and diminishes completely towards Darmstadt (Mezger et al., 2013).

The southwestern part of the Lichtwiese campus is characterized by granites and granodiorites of the Frankenstein Complex, overlain by Quaternary sediments reaching depths of approx. 6 m. The alteration zone down to the unweathered basement is assumed to extend to a depth of approx. 30 m (Greifenhagen, 2000). In contrast, the northeastern portion of the campus Permian basalts, andesites, as well as arkoses, sandstones, and mudstones can be found (Al-Malabeh and Kempe, 2009).

Preliminary seismic investigations, including geoelectric surveys, gravimetry, and reflection seismic methods, confirmed the presence of

crystalline basement immediately beneath the Quaternary cover layers at the planned site (Seib et al., 2024). Evidence of the Permian sedimentary layers, as they are found to the east of the campus, could not be found. Due to subtle contrasts in density and seismic impedance, a detailed classification of crystalline rock types and an assessment of their alteration states could only be accurately determined through direct exposure from drilling activities, specifically via the groundwater monitoring wells (GMW 1-3) and the initial BHE.

2.3. Groundwater monitoring wells

Before the installation of the BHE, three 5" groundwater monitoring wells (GMW 1-3) were drilled using an 8.5" pneumatic down-the-hole (DTH) hammer. The wells were arranged in a triangular layout around the planned MD-BTES system, based on the north to north-east groundwater flow direction according to the hydrogeological map (Seib et al., 2022). Maximum drilling depth ended at 26.5 m to 36.5 m when encountering the more competent section in the basalt unit (Fig. 4).

The extracted drill cuttings were geologically classified and analysed

Fig. 4. Design of the three groundwater monitoring wells (GMW 1-3).

Fig. 5. Drone shot of the demo-site SKEWS during the drilling phase (modified after Landau et al. (2023)).

to determine petrophysical properties using polarized light microscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), and density measurements. Based on these results with the encounter of the crystalline bedrock, the length of the 10 3/4" surface casing of the BHEs was reduced from the planned 100 m to 40 m. Groundwater was encountered at depths of approximately 5 m to 6 m below the ground surface at the time of drilling. To verify the local northward groundwater flow direction and to determine the aquifer's transmissivity, a short-term pumping test was conducted.

For comprehensive monitoring, a multi-parameter logger was installed in the GMW to record hourly measurements of temperature, pH, redox potential, electrical conductivity, and dissolved oxygen. Additionally, a fiber-optic cable was installed for high-resolution depth-specific temperature measurements. Weekly on-site measurements and sampling were also conducted for chemical and biological analyses using ICP-MS and ion chromatography (IC). This monitoring framework was designed to assess whether thermal and/or chemical impacts on the upper aquifer may occur during the drilling phase and operation of the MD-BTES system.

Regarding the evaluation of groundwater monitoring data, no specific data treatment was applied, although it should be noted that there were occasional interruptions of the loggers and one-site measurements. Due to the long monitoring period, sampling and measurements were conducted by different personnel, which constitutes a potential source of methodological error. To verify the measurement results, selected samples were subjected to duplicate analyses. Additionally, in spring 2023, a major construction site with an excavation pit was established approx. 20 m north of GMW 3. Despite a northward groundwater flow direction, the infiltration of foreign substances into the upper aquifer during this period, and thus a possible influence on the groundwater monitoring data, cannot be fully excluded.

2.4. Construction of BHE

The drilling site was built on an area of approx. 2500 m² and included a mud preparation plant, material storage, energy supply, and crew containers (Fig. 5). To install the 750 m deep BHE, a movable universal drilling rig with a hook load capacity of 50 tonnes was utilized, allowing for flexible relocation.

Due to the lack of a permanent power connection at the time of construction, the primary energy supply for the drilling activities was provided by diesel supplies. The drilling rig, two 450 kW mud pumps, two 500 kW compressors with boosters, and various smaller drilling machines were fuelled separately.

A 350 kVA diesel-powered generator supplied electricity to the mud treatment facility during drilling operations. Outside the drilling operation, a separate 100 kVA generator provided power for smaller pumps, smaller electrical devices, site lighting, and crew container facilities.

Based on the preliminary exploration results, the pneumatic and hydraulic DTH hammer drilling methods were selected for the crystalline bedrock. The pneumatic DTH hammer method should be employed to a depth of 400 m, beyond which the Wassara W150.121 hydraulic DTH hammer should be utilized down to 750 m (Fig. 6) (LKAB Wassara, 2015). Due to the predominantly percussion-driven penetration of the hydraulic DTH hammer, which is vertically oriented and aligned with gravitational acceleration within homogeneous crystalline rock formations, improved verticality and enhanced drilling progress compared to conventional rotary drilling (RD) were expected (Staysko et al., 2011), (Bruce et al., 2015).

Initially, only water without additives was intended for circulation to increase environmental sustainability and reduce drilling costs. However, during drilling operation, the drilling method had to be changed due to encountering a fault zone deeply altered basalts up to approx. 160–180 m, which resulted in borehole instability, high fracture densities with substantial water inflows during pneumatic DTH hammer drilling, and significant fluid losses during hydraulic DTH hammer drilling (Landau et al., 2023), (Sass et al., 2025). Hence, the addition of clay-polymer drilling additives was necessary to stabilise the borehole wall and reduce losses, which also required switching the drilling technique from hydraulic DTH to the RD method. To prevent downtime

Table 1

Data treatment of the drilling datas with filter range and rolling mean. The rolling mean of the pumping pressure for the DTH hammers was set to 5.

Drilling data	Unit	Filter range	Rolling mean [s]
ROP	m·h ⁻¹	0-50	1000
WOB	kN	0.1-250	500
Pumping Pressure	Bar	0.01-250	500 (5)
Flow rate	L·min ⁻¹	200-1,500	500
Torque	Nm	200-15,000	500
Rotational speed	RPM	18-120	500

Fig. 6. Drilling bits with a diameter of 9.5" used for the 3 BHEs. A = pneumatic DTH hammer; B = hydraulic DTH hammer; Tricone bit for RD (modified after Landau et al. (2023)).

Fig. 7. Scheme of the drilling fluid circulation system (modified after Landau et al. (2023)).

and exceeding the planned drilling volume, a revised concept was developed jointly with the project partners and the funding agency within a few days and was subsequently approved by the responsible mining authority. The early and intensive involvement of the relevant authorities ultimately ensured the rapid authorization of the change in drilling technique and contributed decisively to the success of the project. However, as an increase in costs was anticipated due to the use of drilling fluid additives, additional cementations and the extended drilling duration, the central borehole BHE 1 had to be cancelled. Nevertheless, a triangular layout with the remaining three boreholes BHE 2–4 could be retained, enabling the investigation of borehole interaction and storage effects during the one-year testing phase.

Before drilling, a 15" surface casing was installed for each of the four BHE down to the top of the bedrock at a depth of 40 m. This was conducted to minimize potential hydraulic and thermal impacts on or induced by the upper aquifer. The actual drilling operations were executed without telescoping, using a 9.5" drill bit down to the final depth of 750 m. Parameters such as weight on bit (WOB), rotational speed (RPM), and torque, rate of penetration (ROP), pumping rate, and pressure, as well as fluid losses, were continuously recorded for each borehole at the drilling rig in one-second intervals.

Regarding data treatment, filtering and the application of a rolling mean were performed on the drilling data to enable improved visual representation, since short-term fluctuations in the range of seconds do not reflect the overall trend of the drilling parameters (Table 1). Only those data points recorded in conjunction with a change in depth or drilling progress were included in this analysis.

The solid-liquid separation of the drilling fluid was carried out using hydrocyclones, shakers, and a centrifuge equipped with a flocculation station. The schematic of the drilling fluid circulation system is depicted in Fig. 7. Initially, the entire slurry was directed over the lower three-layer shaker screen with a mesh size of 0.8 mm to separate the largest drill cuttings directly. These cuttings were sampled at intervals of 2 m, subjected to geological description, and partly examined via thin-section analyses and XRD measurements. The undersized fraction from this screening step was routed into chamber 1, the sand trap, and subsequently pumped into the hydrocyclone, which had a nominal separation cut-point of approx. 20 μm . The undersized overflow from the hydrocyclone was discharged into Chamber 2, which was hydraulically interconnected with Chambers 3 and 4. The oversized underflow, in turn, was processed on the upper triple-deck shaker screen equipped with meshes between 44 and 88 μm , before being returned to Chamber 1 and subsequently recirculated through the hydrocyclone.

To prevent excessive clay accumulation in the drilling fluid, a centrifuge combined with a flocculation station, providing a separation cut-point of approx. 10 μm , was employed as a bypass connected to chambers 2 and 3. Following the shift to RD with a clay-polymer fluid, a polymer dosing system with a separate preparation chamber was

Table 2

Geophysical exploration program to characterise the (hydro-)geological subsurface conditions.

Drilling	BHE 2	BHE 3	BHE 3	BHE 4	BHE 4
Depth	703 m	145 m	745 m	249 m	750 m
Gamma Ray	x	x	x		x
Spectral Gamma Ray	x	x			
Temperature	x	x	x		x
Suszeptibility	x	x			
Resistivity	x				
Electrical Resistivity	x	x			
Accoustic Televiwer		x	x		x
Sonic	x				
Caliper	x	x	x	x	x
Wellbore Orientation	x	x	x	x	x

installed at chamber 4 for mixing the drilling fluid suspension. Downstream of chamber 4, the 450 kW mud pumps transported the conditioned drilling fluid through the drill string to the drill bit at the borehole bottom.

The effectiveness of the cleaning system was evaluated by monitoring the solid content of the drilling fluid at various locations, including directly at the borehole outlet, within chamber 2, at the centrifuge discharge, and in chamber 4.

The clay-polymer drilling fluid primarily consisted of sodium bentonite and calcium carbonate, with calcium-carbonate bridging agents for density adjustment and filtration control (Davoodi et al., 2024). Polymers governed rheology and filtration, using a xanthan polysaccharide as the primary viscosifier and low-viscosity cellulose derivatives (PAC-LV and CMC-LV), for filtration control.

Water chemistry was conditioned with sodium carbonate and sodium bicarbonate, with citric acid applied intermittently for decalcification and controlled pH reduction after intermediate cementations. Potassium chloride provided shale inhibition when required.

Operational additives were applied on demand, including a silicone defoamer and a non-oxidizing biocide. Loss circulation was mitigated with particulate and flake materials such as micronized calcium carbonate, mica and crushed nutshells in medium and coarse grades.

Anionic polyacrylamide flocculants supported solids control and wastewater treatment rather than the circulating mud.

Monitoring of drilling fluid parameters, including rheology, density, solids content, pH, chloride concentration, and hardness, was conducted at least three times daily by drilling fluid engineers at chamber 4. These investigations were done as part of quality assurance and did not reveal any significant anomalies, so they are not included in the results of this study.

Fig. 8. Geometry of the single-mode fiber located in the grout and fixation on the outer 7" BHE pipe with a centralizer (modified after Seib et al. (2025)).

Fig. 9. Design of the coaxial BHE at the SKEWS site with D = Diameter, L = Length, OD = Outer Diameter, ID = Inner Diameter, SC = Surface casing. The inner blue pipe is a composite pipe of PPR and steel (Altherr et al., 1999). Only the width is true to scale (modified after Krusemark et al. (2025)).

2.5. Geophysical measurements and well completion

After drilling the BHEs, a comprehensive geophysical exploration program was conducted in all boreholes to characterize the crystalline reservoir (Table 2). Due to the different geological and hydrogeological conditions encountered, additional borehole geophysical surveys were performed in boreholes BHE 3 and 4 at depths of 144 m and 249 m. These supplementary investigations, combined with cutting analyses

collected during drilling, enabled the (hydro-)geological assessment of fault zones and provided the basis for a switch to rotary drilling with a clay-polymer mud (Sass et al., 2025).

Following this, a 7" steel casing was installed, which represents the outer wall of the coaxial BHE. For depth-resolved determination of the thermal BHE and subsurface properties, a single-mode fiber optic cable was attached to the centralizer on the outside of the 7" casing for all boreholes (Fig. 8). The loose-tube fibers enabled depth-resolved

temperature profiling and acoustic signal recording. Additionally, tight-buffer fibers were utilized for strain measurements, enabling the monitoring of thermal expansion in response to the charging and discharging of the MD-BTES.

The backfilling of the 750 m BHE involved two distinct cement types to optimize thermal performance. From the surface down to a depth of approximately 150–180 m, a cement with low thermal conductivity of $0.6 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ was utilized to minimize thermal interference with the upper aquifer (Fig. 9). Below this transition zone, a thermally enhanced cement with a thermal conductivity of approx. $3.0 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$ was used to enhance heat transfer into the surrounding rock formation.

During the construction of the first BHE, the cementation was performed using two plugs. Initially, the low thermal conductive, air-voided cement was injected, followed by thermally enhanced cement, which was pumped into the annulus from bottom to top. However, due to difficulties in accurately estimating the required cement volumes and the creation of a several-meter mixing zone between the two cement types, the BHE 2 and 4 were backfilled using a stage-tool (Association de Recherche sur les Techniques d'Exploitation du Pétrole, 1993). By installing the stage-tool at a depth of 150–160 m, a more defined boundary between the two cement types could be established.

The completion of the BHE with the patented 4½-inch steel-PPR composite pipe and the wellhead was carried out in 2023 (Handke et al., 2019). Additionally, a multimode fiber-optic cable was installed within the annulus of all BHEs for high-resolution depth-specific temperature measurements. In BHE 2, an additional fiber-optic cable was also installed within the inner pipe. Through distributed geothermal response tests, further investigations were conducted, particularly on the thermal properties of the patented steel-PPR composite inner pipe (Seib et al., 2025).

3. Results and discussion

The following section presents the results of the project phase 4 – the drilling phase – with a focus on the evaluation of the drilling data, considering the encountered geological conditions as well as the associated ecological impacts. Due to the large amount of data collected, only a selection of the results is presented in this manuscript. The other research results described in the methodology will be published in subsequent publications.

3.1. Drilling progress

The surface casing from 0 to 40 m depth was installed for BHE 1–4 in June 2022 over a period of approx. three weeks. The subsequent deep drilling phase of BHE 2–4, including site preparation, relocation of the drilling rig, and other interruptions, was conducted from early July 2022

until the end of October 2022. The installation of the inner tubing and the wellhead was carried out in August 2023 and required approx. three weeks.

Fig. 10 illustrates the drilling progress of the deep boreholes, starting with BHE 4 and finishing with BHE 2, expressed in days. As previously noted in Chapter 2.4, the drilling methodology had to be changed to rotary drilling with clay-polymer mud due to the encounter of a fault zone with borehole instability. The Wassera W150.121 hydraulic hammer system could only be tested under limited conditions, as it was specifically designed for operation with pure water containing a maximum particle size of $50 \mu\text{m}$ and a solid content of $150 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (LKAB Wassara, 2015). Tests conducted with clay-polymer drilling mud resulted in clogging of the internal valves, which in turn inhibited the impact mechanism (Tuomas, 2001). This is because, when using drilling mud, the separation of fine particles $> 50 \mu\text{m}$ becomes significantly more difficult due to its higher density and viscosity. Moreover, the solid content of approximately 2 % by volume substantially exceeded the system's design threshold of $150 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. Mud-compatible hydraulic DTH are being investigated in numerous studies with respect to mud density, wear, drill bits and overall performance (Teodoriu, 2012), (Souchal et al., 2017), (Ge et al., 2020), (Gerbaud et al., 2023). However, within the framework of this project, such systems could not be tested due to the time-critical methodological change and the general problem of borehole instability. Repeated testing of the hydraulic hammer and the temporary switching of the circulation fluid back to water without additives resulted in increased interruptions and round trips. Furthermore, intermediate cementing between 40–180 m and 40–250 m was required in all three boreholes to stabilize the wellbores. In addition, in the first borehole (BHE 3), a fracture zone was encountered at approx. 550 m depth had to be sealed through an additional intermediate cementing, which also closed the fracture zones in BHE 3 and BHE 2. Additional interruptions were required due to geophysical borehole logging activities as well as a repair of the drilling rig. Overall, the drilling duration could be reduced from the initial 32.2 days to 23.3 days as drilling experience increased over the course of the project. When excluding the time required for scientific experiments (hydraulic hammer tests and geophysical logging) and the rig repair, the effective drilling times were 23.0 days for BHE 3, 18.6 days for BHE 4, and 16.3 days for BHE 2.

3.2. Drilling data

3.2.1. Geology, mud losses and cementing

In Fig. 11, the mud losses and intermediate cementing operations, as well as the key drilling parameters, including rate of penetration (ROP), pump pressure, flow rate, weight on bit (WOB), torque, and rotational speed in round per minutes (RPM) are presented in relation to depth and

Fig. 10. Drilling progress of the three BHE with interruptions due to fluid hammer testing, cementing, geophysical surveys and drill rig repairs. BHE 3 was the first drilling, followed by BHE 4 and finally BHE 2 (modified after Landau et al. (2023)).

Fig. 11. Drilling profiles of BHE 2–4 with mud losses, the rate of penetration (ROP), weight on bit (WOB), Pumping pressure, flow rate, torque and rotational speed in round per minutes (RPM) and 3D view of the bore hole path deviations (modified after Landau et al. (2023) and Krusemark et al. (2025)).

Table 3

Backfill quantities of the intermediate cementations in BHE 2–4 with borehole section volume.

Interim Cementations	Depth [m]		Borehole [m ³]	Cement [m ³]	Spacer [m ³]
	from	to			
BHE 3 (1st)	36.5	77.5	1.9	3.1	2
	77.5	180	4.7	6.1	3.2
BHE 3 (2nd)	344	515	7.8	7.5	4.7
	515	550	1.6	7	5.7
BHE 4	12	250	10.9	12	5.5
BHE 2	24	250	10.3	11	5

correlated with the geological profile. In general, these parameters vary depending on (hydro-)geological conditions, the materials employed, borehole diameter, drilling depth, and the operational settings chosen by the drilling engineer. Consequently, a direct comparison of characteristic values from other projects is only of limited applicability. For contextualization of the results, however, data from comparable projects in Soultz-sous-Forêts, Rittershoffen, Insheim and Basel with hard-rock conditions suggest expected ROP in the range of 10–30 m·h⁻¹ for pneumatic DTH drilling, 5–15 m·h⁻¹ for hydraulic DTH drilling, and 2–10 m·h⁻¹ for RD (Baujard et al., 2017), (Su et al., 2017), (Cao et al., 2025). Benchmarking of mud- and water-driven hammers in deep tests likewise shows ROP gains by factors of 2–5 compared to conventional RD when fluid properties and bit design are optimised (Tibbitts et al., 2002), (Staysko et al., 2011). The geological profile was developed based on petrophysical cutting analyses and borehole geophysical measurements (Landau et al., 2023), (Sass et al., 2025). The results indicate that up to depths of approx. 160–180 m, strongly altered basalts with intersections of sandstones and siltstones were encountered, underlain by partially highly altered granites. From approx. 460 m depth, the granites transition into granodiorites characterized by higher strength and reduced fracturing.

Particularly within the strongly altered basalts and granites, significant mud losses were observed, reaching up to 86 m³·d⁻¹. During the use of the pneumatic DTH hammer up to a depth of 127 m, substantial water inflows of approximately 30 m³·h⁻¹ occurred, which, before the switch to RD, were refilled into the borehole. Another major fracture zone was encountered at approx. 515 m depth within the granodiorite, which resulted in mud losses of up to 94 m³·d⁻¹. To mitigate these losses, the drilling technique was adapted to rotary drilling with a clay-polymer mud. In addition, intermediate cementing operations were performed down to depths of approx. 180 m and 250 m, as well as between 344–550 m in BHE 3. For sealing the fractures, a limestone-based lost circulation material was applied, followed by cementation. The respective cement volumes used are summarized in Table 3. The cement loss of 5.4 m³ at a depth of 515–550 m at BHE 3 also indicates the presence of a highly fractured fault zone.

3.2.2. Drilling data – basalt

In BHE 3, the pneumatic DTH hammer achieved high ROP ranging from approx. 12–30 m·h⁻¹ down to a depth of 127 m. These results were obtained with relatively low WOB between 10–70 kN and moderate torque values ranging from 800–2500 Nm. Following the transition to the rotary drilling method, the ROP decreased significantly to approx. 5 m·h⁻¹ within the basaltic formations. The WOB similarly fluctuated between 10–70 kN, while the torque was around 2500 Nm. Pump pressure was measured between approximately 2–5 bar, with flow rates in the range of 1100–1400 L·min⁻¹.

In BHE 4, the rotary drilling process was started directly, resulting in lower ROP values of approx. 4–10 m·h⁻¹. The WOB were comparable, between 10–60 kN, with torque values ranging from 1500–3500 Nm and rotational speeds between 50–70 rpm. The pumping pressure increased up to 10 bar, while flow rates were approx. 800–900 L·min⁻¹. In BHE 2,

the hydraulic DTH hammer system was employed down to a depth of approx. 86 m, using water without additives. In this interval, ROP values between 10–25 m·h⁻¹ were achieved, with WOB of approx. 10–25 kN, torque ranging from 2000–3700 Nm, and rotational speeds of 22–42 rpm. Pump pressures ranged from 60–75 bar, at flow rates of approx. 580–620 L·min⁻¹. From 86 to 160 m depth, drilling was switched back to rotary with clay-polymer mud. In this phase, ROP declined to approx. 3–15 m·h⁻¹. WOB and rotational speed increased to approx. 20–55 kN and 35–75 rpm, respectively, with torque remaining similar at 2500–3700 Nm. Pump pressures decreased to 2–4 bar, with flow rates of 800–1000 L·min⁻¹.

Accordingly, under comparable geological conditions in the altered basalt, the pneumatic and hydraulic DTH hammer methods achieved ROP values approximately 3–5 times higher than those of the RD method. WOB, rotational speeds, and flow rates were generally lower in the DTH hammer systems due to the percussive energy being generated directly within the hammer (Tuomas and Nordell, 2000), (Bruce et al., 2015). However, given the low strength of the highly altered basalt down to approx. 160 m depth, the WOB and torque in rotary drilling remained relatively moderate.

3.2.3. Drilling data – Lichtwiese granite

The Lichtwiese granite was drilled almost entirely using the rotary method with clay-polymer mud in all boreholes, except for a section between 200 m and 233 m depth in BHE 3. Across all three boreholes, average ROP ranged from approx. 2–9 m·h⁻¹. ROP generally decreased with increasing depth but locally increased to 9–13 m·h⁻¹ within highly altered zones. The WOB showed an inverse trend relative to ROP. In the highly altered intervals, WOB remained low at approx. 10 kN, increasing progressively with greater rock strength and depth to values up to around 60 kN. Pump pressures and flow rates remained nearly constant during rotary drilling, at approx. 3–5 bar and 900–1200 L·min⁻¹. Torque increased continuously with depth, ranging from approx. 2000–5500 Nm. This can be attributed both to the increasing strength of the granite and to greater friction between the drill string and the borehole wall, as the boreholes were not drilled precisely vertical. Rotational speeds ranged between 70–90 rpm in general, while in strongly altered zones the rotational speed decreased to approximately 50–65 rpm. In the section from 200 m to 233 m depth in BHE 3, which was drilled using the hydraulic DTH hammer, the ROP increased abruptly from approx. 3 m·h⁻¹ up to 13 m·h⁻¹. Pumping pressures during this phase reached 75 bar, with flow rates of approx. 380 L·min⁻¹.

3.2.4. Drilling data – Darmstadt granodiorite

The Darmstadt granodiorite was also drilled almost entirely using the RD method with clay-polymer mud circulation, except for the intervals between 660–667 m in BHE 3 and 549–555 m in BHE 4, where the hydraulic DTH hammer was employed. Additionally, in BHE 2, a downhole motor was used between 464–594 m to increase the ROP. However, the ROP remained consistently low at approx. 3–6 m·h⁻¹, and high torque levels of up to 8000 Nm were observed. Consequently, the motor was removed from the drilling assembly. Due to the hydraulic drive of the downhole motor, flow rates and pump pressures also increased to 1100–1300 L·min⁻¹ and 25–35 bar, respectively.

In general, ROP in the granodiorite decreased further to approx. 1.5–3 m·h⁻¹ and locally increased to 5–10 m·h⁻¹ in altered zones. WOB also increased with depth and greater rock strength, reaching up to 75 kN, although measurement records for BHE 3 and BHE 4 were incomplete. Pump pressures and flow rates during conventional rotary drilling remained in the range of 3–5 bar and 750–1300 L·min⁻¹. Torque similarly increased with depth, ranging between 3000–6500 Nm. Due to the presence of the fault zone at approx. 550 m, torque temporarily decreased to about 2500 Nm in BHE 4, as the crushing of the altered granodiorite required less energy. Rotational speeds were between 70–90 rpm and decreased in highly altered sections to 45–70 rpm.

In the intervals drilled with the hydraulic down-the-hole hammer,

IC-analyses of GMW 1-3 from March 2022 - July 2023

Fig. 13. Results of the ion chromatographic (IC) analysis of the groundwater monitoring wells GMW 1-3 from March 2022 – July 2023.

ICP-MS analyses of GMW 1-3 from March 2022 – July 2023

Fig. 14. Results of the Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis of the groundwater monitoring wells GMW 1-3 from March 2022 – July 2023.

Fig. 15. Ion balance errors of GMW 1-3 based on the main anions (HCO_3^- , Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-}) and cations (K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+}) from March 2022 - July 2023.

noted, a pronounced rise in groundwater level up to 175 m a.s.l. occurred, followed by a decline to as low as 167.8 m a.s.l. in all three observation wells. This behaviour indicates a hydraulic connection between the shallow aquifer and the deeper fractured aquifer system from approx. 40 m to at least 127 m depth. Two additional abrupt increases in groundwater level of about 1 m were observed, correlating directly with the initiation of drilling operations at BHE 4 and BHE 2. Accordingly, fluid losses in the upper borehole sections induced temporary rises in groundwater level, while losses in deeper sections had no measurable impact on groundwater heads. Upon completion of drilling, groundwater levels recovered to their initial levels around 171 m a.s.l.

Turbidity can be used as a sensitive indicator of groundwater disturbance by drilling fluids or cement (Kang et al., 2016), (Fernandez et al., 2021). Prior to drilling, nephelometric turbidity units (NTU) were close to zero, which is typical for drinking water quality (Kitchener et al., 2017). With the start of deep drilling, turbidity increased in all three wells to between 50-200 NTU, and in GMW 2 to values ranging from 500-1600 NTU, providing clear evidence of particle intrusion from drilling fluids and/or cement slurries. After completion of drilling, turbidity decreased only gradually, likely due to residual particles retained within the pore matrix that were slowly mobilized over time.

Regarding water temperature, almost no variations were observed in the southern well GMW 1. In contrast, GMW 2 and GMW 3, located downstream, exhibited moderate temperature changes of up to 1 °C toward the end of drilling and slight temperature increases beyond the drilling period. The other parameters, including pH, electrical conductivity, dissolved oxygen, redox potential, and bicarbonate, all showed distinct shifts during the drilling phase. Elevated bicarbonate (HCO_3^-) and pH values, as well as increases in electrical conductivity are consistent with interactions between groundwater and drilling mud additives such as sodium carbonate and bicarbonate, which can elevate alkalinity and ionic strength in aquifer systems, as documented for the ATES exploration well in Berlin (Regenspurg et al., 2018). GMW 3, located closest to the boreholes and downgradient, exhibited the most pronounced impact. In GMW 2, dissolved oxygen dropped from ~70 % to ~20 %, while redox potential declined from ~200 mV to ~20 mV. These changes are consistent with the introduction of biodegradable polymers such as xanthan gum and carboxymethyl cellulose, which were used in the water-based drilling fluid. Several studies have shown that such polysaccharide additives are readily degraded by subsurface microbial communities, leading to oxygen consumption and a temporary shift towards more reducing conditions (Cadmus et al., 1982), (Hou

et al., 1986), (Struchtemeyer et al., 2011), (Pellizzari et al., 2017). At the same time, alkaline additives like bentonite and carbonate buffers can elevate pH and conductivity, as observed in other geothermal drilling projects. Following the completion of drilling, redox potential in GMW 2 recovered rapidly to ~350 mV, suggesting that these effects were transient and did not result in long-term alteration of groundwater chemistry, in agreement with findings from comparable field studies (Regenspurg et al., 2018). Due to missing measurements during the pumping test and the installation of the surface casing, potential effects on in-situ parameters during these periods cannot be conclusively assessed.

Fig. 13 presents the ion chromatographic (IC) analysis results from samples taken at the groundwater monitoring wells GMW 1-3. A significant impact of the deep drilling operations on the chemical composition of the groundwater was observed for the anions chloride (Cl^-), nitrite (NO_2^-), nitrate (NO_3^-), sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), and the cations sodium (Na^+), ammonium (NH_4^+), potassium (K^+), magnesium (Mg^{2+}), and calcium (Ca^{2+}). As no samples were taken during the installation of the surface casing and the pumping test, their effects on the chemical changes in the groundwater can only be described to a limited extent. However, the measured values before and after the installation of the surface casing and the pumping test, show for all parameters similar values, indicating that no significant and persistent chemical alteration of the groundwater occurred at that stage.

During the deep drilling phase, Cl^- and K^+ levels in GMW 3 increased from 10-20 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 50-60 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and from 2 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 5 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, respectively, most likely due to the addition of potassium chloride (KCl) to the drilling fluid (Caenn, 2011), (Papakostas et al., 2022). After drilling, chloride concentrations remained elevated at approx. 25-45 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, suggesting a slow back-diffusion from the borehole environment. The increase in SO_4^{2-} from 35-50 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 70-100 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and in Ca^{2+} from approx. 115 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 140-180 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ in GMW 3 is probably linked to the use of bentonite and calcium carbonate in the drilling fluid, as well as leaching of cementitious materials used in casing and borehole sealing (Sasaki et al., 1994), (Kaufhold et al., 2023).

The rise in Na^+ from approximately 10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to 30-50 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ correlates with the use of bentonite and soda ash (Na_2CO_3) to activate the clay minerals (Sasaki et al., 1994). Ion exchange processes likely released Na^+ into the groundwater while Ca^{2+} while Ca^{2+} is taken up by the fluid or precipitated as CaCO_3 (Sasaki et al., 1994). Under conditions of excess Ca^{2+} and rising pH, Mg^{2+} can also be released from the bentonite, a process consistent with the observed increase in Mg^{2+}

Fig. 16. Piper diagrams of the groundwater monitoring wells GMW 1-3 from March 2022 – July 2023 with Total dissolved solids (TDS) in $\text{mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

concentrations from $7 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to $10\text{--}15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ (Wallis et al., 2016).

The intermittent increases in NH_4^+ from $0.6 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to $1.2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and in NO_2^- from approx. $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ to $4\text{--}6 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, together with fluctuating NO_3^- concentrations of around $15\text{--}80 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ are most likely related to the degradation of the cationic polyacrylamide flocculant, which can release ammonium upon hydrolysis and microbial deamination (Xiong et al., 2018), (Nyssölä and Ahlgren, 2019). The subsequent conversion of ammonium to nitrite and nitrate is consistent with the activity of ammonia- and nitrite-oxidizing microorganisms, which are widespread in groundwater aquifers (Daims et al., 2015).

Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analyses revealed substantial temporal variations in 27 trace elements across the three monitoring wells (GMW 1, GMW 2, and GMW 3) during and after the geothermal borehole drilling campaign (Fig. 14, Appendix 1). The most pronounced increases were recorded during the deep drilling phase

(July–October 2022), with distinct patterns depending on element mobility, sorption affinity, and transport behaviour.

Aluminium (Al, $\sim 800 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), iron (Fe, $\sim 3000 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and manganese (Mn, $\sim 200 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) reached high peak concentrations, consistent with reductive dissolution of iron and manganese oxides caused by oxygen depletion during microbial degradation of polymers and the cationic polyacrylamide flocculant in the drilling fluid (Cadmus et al., 1982), (Appelo and Postma, 2004), (Nyssölä and Ahlgren, 2019), (Ferris et al., 2023). This process was further enhanced by the addition of soda ash and other carbonate-based materials, which increased alkalinity and promoted both carbonate–metal complexation and cation competition (Na^+ , Ca^{2+}) at mineral surfaces. These interactions reduced sorption efficiency and thus facilitated mobilization of metals initially bound to mineral phases (Caporale and Violante, 2016).

Chromium (Cr, $\sim 7 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), vanadium (V, $\sim 8 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), nickel (Ni, ~ 40

$\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and cobalt (Co, $\sim 4.8 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) showed co-varying peaks with Fe/Mn, indicating release of trace metals associated with Fe/Mn oxides under reducing conditions (Izbicki et al., 2023).

Copper (Cu, $\sim 300 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) exhibited a delayed peak after active drilling. This pattern is consistent with strong sorption to iron oxide sand mineral colloids, which produces transport retardation. Intermittent remobilisation of colloids together with evolving complexation then produced a delayed arrival (Kooner, 1992).

Zinc (Zn, $\sim 1600 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) showed pronounced spikes. In addition to release from iron and manganese phases, increases in alkalinity and ionic strength together with carbonate and hydroxide complexation can episodically reduce zinc adsorption and increase dissolved zinc, even though increasing pH generally enhances cation adsorption (Casagrande et al., 2004).

Arsenic (As, $\sim 4 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), selenium (Se, $\sim 12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), cadmium (Cd, $\sim 0.6 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), antimony (Sb, $\sim 1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and lead (Pb, $\sim 15 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) occurred at lower absolute levels but rose when redox potential declined, consistent with release from iron oxides by reductive dissolution or desorption (Thomas, 2007).

Strontium (Sr, $\sim 1200 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), barium (Ba, $\sim 800 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and rubidium (Rb, $\sim 12 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) remained elevated for months. This pattern is compatible with ion exchange driven desorption from clays for strontium and rubidium under sodium rich and high alkalinity conditions and with slow precipitation or readsorption kinetics for barium. Barium is buffered by the very low solubility of barite, BaSO_4 . Cesium (Cs, $\sim 2.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) occurred at low concentrations, which potentially reflects ion exchange processes favoured by sodium enrichment of the pore water (Wahlberg et al., 1965).

Titanium (Ti, $\sim 40 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), zirconium (Zr, $\sim 2.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), niobium (Nb, $\sim 1.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), tin (Sn, $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), thallium (Tl, $< 1 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), thorium (Th, $\sim 2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), and uranium (U, $\sim 10 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) were detected only at low levels and are largely immobile under the observed geochemical conditions. Their presence is most plausibly related to minor colloidal transport rather than to true solubilisation.

Molybdenum (Mo, $\sim 7 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) and silver (Ag, $\sim 3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) were detected only intermittently, which suggests episodic mobilisation by transient colloidal dispersions or desorption during periods of changing pH.

An important observation is that Ni, Zn, Se, Sr und Nb were higher in GMW 1 and GMW 2 than in GMW 3, although GMW 3 is closer to the borehole. This pattern suggests that the near-well zone favoured retention of these elements through rapid adsorption to freshly formed or

remaining iron and manganese oxide surfaces, whereas more distal zones received a higher proportion of dissolved and colloid-associated fractions (Mohammadian et al., 2021).

Overall, the temporal patterns indicate that the combined effects of polymer-based drilling fluids, alkalinity adjustment by soda ash and carbonate additives, and rapid redox shifts caused extensive release of trace elements that were primarily bound to mineral phases. While most elements declined clearly after drilling had ceased, strontium and barium remained elevated for several months, which reflects slower ion exchange and precipitation kinetics.

The Fig. 15 illustrates the temporal development of the ion-balance error after Reed and Mariner (1991) for the three groundwater monitoring wells (Reed and Mariner, 1991). In hydrochemical data-quality control, a deviation within about ± 5 percent (dashed lines) is widely used as an acceptance criterion when major ions are expressed in milliequivalents per litre (DIN, 2024). The exceedances beyond ± 5 percent during the deep-drilling period are plausibly explained by process-related hydrochemical disturbances induced by RD with bentonite-polymer mud. GMW 2 shows several pronounced outliers, reaching deviations of approx. $+15\%$ and -25% . The use of clay-polymer drilling fluids and intermittent cementation introduced substantial dissolved constituents, notably chloride, sulfate, sodium and calcium, producing abrupt shifts in ionic composition. Such additions need not affect all major cations and anions proportionally, which can temporarily distort electroneutrality checks. Elevated turbidity and increased salinity during drilling likely reduced analytical accuracy for some ions. The subsequent return of ion-balance errors toward the acceptance range after drilling indicates that the exceedances were primarily transient and process-related rather than indicative of persistent geochemical disequilibrium.

The Piper diagram indicates that the groundwater samples consistently plot within the calcium–magnesium bicarbonate facies, reflecting a hydrochemical composition characteristic of shallow to intermediate depth groundwater equilibrated with carbonate-bearing and silicate bedrock (Fig. 16). This facies is widespread in many shallow groundwater systems due to carbonate dissolution and CO_2 -driven weathering processes and is frequently observed also in fractured crystalline rocks where secondary carbonate veins and weathering of mafic and plagioclase minerals supply Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and HCO_3^- (Gastmans et al., 2016). The tight clustering of samples within this field suggests a relatively homogeneous hydrochemical evolution across monitoring periods and wells, despite transient processes potentially influencing solute mobilization.

Fig. 17. Diesel consumption per consumer during the deep drilling phase.

Fig. 18. Energy consumption from the 350 kVA and 150 kVA generators per consumer during the deep drilling phase.

Overall, the prevalence of this facies in the Piper diagram is consistent with expected baseline groundwater quality in such geological settings and indicates that no persistent shift toward more saline or chemically evolved water types has occurred over the observation period.

3.3.2. Energy and water consumption

The energy consumption associated with the construction of the deep boreholes is illustrated in Figs. 17 and 18. At the time of the drilling operations, there was no electrical connection between the drilling site and the Lichtwiese Campus, so that so all the energy had to be supplied by diesel deliveries. Fig. 17 shows the fuel consumption of individual consumers. The largest share was accounted for by the 350 kVA generator, which consumed 41,500 L, followed by the drilling rig with 25,300 L, and the two mud pumps with 15,600 L and 2280 L, respectively. The 100 kVA generator had a relatively low consumption of only 2,620 L and was operated outside the drilling periods when the 350 kVA unit was not required. The two compressors were used only intermittently during the operation of the pneumatic DTH hammer, resulting in comparatively low consumption of 260 L and 1,160 L. The demand of auxiliary equipment on site (truck and wheel loader) amounted to a total of 2,290 L. Accordingly, the overall diesel demand for the drilling project was approximately 90,950 L, i.e. roughly 30,000 L per borehole or about 40 L·m⁻¹, which corresponds to about 244 t of CO₂, assuming an emission factor of 2.68 kg CO₂ per liter of diesel (Jubrich, 2022). If a grid connection to supply the site with electricity had been available, the use of the two generators could have been avoided, thereby saving approximately 43,120 L of diesel, i.e. roughly 19 L·m⁻¹, and about 116 t of CO₂ emissions. Further reductions in emissions could be achieved in the future by transitioning to electrically powered pumping systems and drilling rigs. In comparison, the deep geothermal doublet case study in Banchory (Scotland) assumes a diesel demand of 3785 L·day⁻¹ and a drilling time of 1500 h per 2000 m well, which is equivalent to ~236, 500 L per well or ~118 L·m⁻¹ and ~634 t CO₂ per well (McCay et al., 2019). A recent operational study on a petroleum and geothermal drilling rig reports that, under representative drilling parameters at 1281–1385 m depth, a 24 h drilling interval with rate of penetration of about 4.5 m·h⁻¹ consumed 12,241 L of diesel, equivalent to ~110–120 L·m⁻¹ (Yildiz and Yilmaz, 2024). A direct comparison of the fuel consumption rates reported in the two studies with those at the SKEWS site is not straightforward, as the former use much larger drilling rigs and mud pumps due to greater drilling depths. Nonetheless, the Banchory case study indicates that, when life-cycle CO₂ intensity over the operational period is considered, the investigated systems exhibit lower emissions and are therefore preferable to fossil-fuel-based heat supply.

Fig. 18 shows the electrical consumption of the two generators with

capacities of 150 kVA and 350 kVA. In total, approximately 111,460 kWh of electrical energy were provided. The demand associated with mud treatment processes (separation, centrifuge, and flocculation unit) accounted for 40,020 kWh, while the remaining 71,440 kWh were required to cover the general electricity demand of the facilities, including site lighting, heating and smaller pumps.

Considering the total diesel consumption of the generators, amounting to 43,120 L, and the generated electrical energy of 111,460 kWh, this results in an overall efficiency of only 26.4 %, based on a diesel energy content of 9.8 kWh per liter. According to the manufacturer, the efficiency of the 350 kVA generator under full load conditions is approximately 37 %. Thus, it can be assumed that, due to the variable energy demand during drilling operations, the generator frequently operated under partial load, which significantly reduced its efficiency. Therefore, connecting the site to an existing power grid would enable demand-driven electricity supply and would substantially reduce CO₂ emissions.

The water consumption during the deep drilling operations amounted to a total of 1,646 m³ and was primarily used for mud treatment. In principle, the operation relied on a closed-loop circulation system, however, losses of drilling fluid had to be compensated. Furthermore, whenever tests with the hydraulic DTH hammer were conducted, the entire mud treatment system was flushed and refilled with fresh water without additives. Consequently, the scientific testing of the hydraulic DTH hammer led to multiple replacements of the drilling fluid, resulting in increased water consumption.

3.4. Limitations of the case study

As a first MD-BTES of its kind in crystalline basement, the SKEWS demonstration site represents a single, site-specific case. The drilling results, ecological impacts and energy demands documented here are therefore not directly transferable to other geological settings, particularly to less fractured crystalline rocks or to sedimentary formations. Highly altered basalts, a major fault zone strongly influenced mud losses, borehole stability, drilling performance and groundwater responses. In more homogeneous or less permeable settings, both the operational challenges and the environmental footprint of drilling may differ substantially.

A second limitation is related to drilling technology and operational constraints. The pneumatic and hydraulic down-the-hole (DTH) hammers, which achieved significantly higher rates of penetration than rotary drilling, could only be used over limited depth intervals because clay-polymer drilling fluid became necessary to stabilise the boreholes in highly altered zones. Mud-compatible DTH hammers, and alternative

high-performance drilling concepts were not available for systematic testing. In addition, directional drilling was not applied for cost reasons, so that the influence of active trajectory control on storage layout and performance could not be assessed. As a result, the documented borehole deviations and drilling times represent the outcome of a specific combination of technologies, learning effects and geological conditions rather than a fully optimized industrial MD-BTES drilling concept.

The environmental monitoring and hydrochemical assessment are likewise subject to limitations. Groundwater monitoring was restricted to three shallow observation wells in the upper aquifer and to a period of about 17 months, with some gaps and changes in sampling personnel. While the available data show a clear trend back towards baseline conditions and no persistent shift away from calcium-magnesium bicarbonate water type, subtle long-term changes in trace elements, redox-sensitive species or microbial communities cannot be entirely excluded.

Finally, the analysis of energy demand and CO₂ emissions focuses solely on the drilling phase of the demonstration project. Only the diesel consumption of the rig, mud pumps, compressors and generators was quantified, whereas upstream emissions embedded in steel, cement and drilling additives, as well as the operational electricity demand of the MD-BTES and the district heating network, are not yet included. In this context, the drilling-related energy demand and CO₂ emissions reported here should be interpreted as an upper-bound estimate for a research-driven demonstration project, to be refined by techno-economic and life-cycle analyses.

4. Conclusion and outlook

From 2022 to 2023, the SKEWS MD-BTES consisting of three BHEs with depths up to 750 m arranged in a triangular layout with a spacing of 8.6 m was constructed at the Lichtwiese Campus in Darmstadt. The results demonstrate the technical feasibility within the tightly constrained timeframe and budget of the SKEWS research project, with a focus on the collected drilling data as well as the ecological impacts. In contrast to most previous MD-BTES research, which has largely been based on analytical and numerical studies (Homuth et al., 2013; Bär et al., 2015; Welsch et al., 2015; Welsch, 2019; Welsch et al., 2016; Kolo et al., 2024; Formhals et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2024; Welsch et al., 2018), this case study provides one of the first comprehensive empirical data sets on drilling performance, groundwater response and energy demand for a medium-deep storage system in crystalline basement.

Three of the four planned BHEs were successfully constructed to the target final depth of 750 m as originally designed. However, due to unforeseen (hydro-)geological conditions, including the encounter of a fault zone and deeply altered basalts and granites, the drilling technology had to be switched from pneumatic and hydraulic DTH hammer drilling to RD with a clay-polymer drilling fluid. This transition, along with intermediate cementations for borehole stabilization, was associated with increasing costs.

The hydraulic DTH hammer could only be tested over limited intervals but demonstrated drilling rates that were 2-5 times higher than the rotary method. In compact crystalline bedrock with limited fracturing, this technique has the potential to significantly reduce drilling time and consequently lower costs. Furthermore, for future projects, the ability of hydraulic or mud-driven DTH hammers to maintain borehole verticality and to operate reliably with drilling fluids should be systematically assessed.

Analysis of the drilling data revealed a strong correlation with the

(hydro-)geological conditions encountered. This suggests that in large-scale borehole fields, there is potential to apply deep learning techniques to train an AI model capable of predicting drilling progress based on the recorded parameters. Such tools could support real-time decision-making, reduce non-productive time and improve the planning reliability of commercial MD-BTES projects.

An ecological impact on groundwater was documented during the drilling phase. It was observed that, despite sealing the borehole with a surface casing to a depth of 40 m, a pronounced hydraulic connection existed between the upper aquifer and the fractured bedrock aquifer. For subsequent drilling campaigns, it may be advisable to install the surface casing at greater depths. However, for most parameters, the influence on groundwater diminished rapidly after drilling concluded, and no sustained negative impacts are expected.

The evaluation of CO₂ emissions associated with borehole construction is a critical component of the overall assessment of renewable energy technologies. Significant emission reductions can be achieved by implementing direct grid connections and transitioning to electrically driven pump systems and drilling rigs.

The storage system has now been put into practice through a one-year test operation and a successful integration into the district heating network of TU Darmstadt. The resulting measurement data will be made publicly available, allowing researchers to analyse the system's real-world performance with this study. These data sets provide a valuable basis for validating simulation models, optimizing system design parameters, and conducting comparative studies for future MD-BTES implementations.

In addition, a levelized cost of heat (LCOH) analysis will be performed, with a particular focus on comparing the costs of scientific and commercial drilling and on clearly identifying the individual cost components. Based on the analysis of drilling times, which indicates an approx. 30 % reduction in drilling duration between the first and third boreholes, a substantial decrease in total drilling costs can be anticipated for a full-scale storage expansion under commercial drilling conditions.

Overall, this study shows that the construction of a MD-BTES in a crystalline basement with high operating temperatures is technically feasible and environmentally manageable with current drilling technology. At the same time, it identifies clear optimization potentials, such as deeper surface casings in fractured zones, mud-compatible DTH hammer systems, cost-optimized vertical drilling, and electrification of drilling operations to reduce CO₂ emissions. These findings provide guidance for future MD-BTES projects and help to position this technology as a robust solution for decarbonising district heating networks.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Matthias Krusemark: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Lukas Seib:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Hung Pham:** Writing – review & editing. **Ingo Sass:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix

ICP-MS analyses of GMW 1-3 from March 2022 - July 2023

Appendix 1. Results of the Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis of the groundwater monitoring wells GMW 1-3 from March 2022 - July 2023.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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